

Functional Studies of Iron Oxidation in *Gallionellaceae* sp. Culture KS

Localisation of the Cytochrome Domaine in the Outer
Membrane Protein Cyc2

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Bachelor Thesis in Environmental Science

Center for Applied Geoscience
Geomicrobiology Group
Eberhard Karls University of Tübingen
March 2021

Acronyms

AlSO₄ · 16 H₂O aluminium sulphate hexadecahydrate. 19

CaCl₂ · 2 H₂O calcium chloride dihydrate. 21

CaCl₂ calcium chloride. 21

H₂O₂ hydrogen peroxide. 28

KCl potassium chloride. 21, 22

KOH potassium hydroxide. 21

MgCl₂ · 6 H₂O magnesium chloride hexahydrate. 20

MgCl₂ magnesium chloride. 20, 22

MgSO₄ · 7 H₂O magnesium sulphate heptahydrate. 20

MgSO₄ magnesium sulphate. 20, 22

MnCl₂ · 4 H₂O manganese chloride tetrahydrate. 21

MnCl₂ manganese chloride. 21

N₂ nitrogen. 25

NaCl sodium chloride. 21–23

NaOH sodium hydroxide. 19, 20

E. coli *escherichia coli*. 2–4, 14, 18, 23, 24, 26, 33, 35, 39, 41, 45

***cyc2*_{Gal}** *cyc2* gene of *Gallionellaceae* sp. culture KS. 23–26, 33, 35–37, 39, 40, 42

ompA gene sequence of outer membrane protein A. 24, 35, 39

ompF gene sequence of outer membrane protein F. 41

a.a. amino acid. 14, 15, 24, 25, 33–35, 39, 41

ACA 6-aminocaproic acid. 18, 19

AHTC anhydrotetracycline hydrochloride. 19, 23, 26

APS ammonium persulfate. 19, 28

- BAM** β -barrel assembly machinery. 17, 41, 42, 44
- Bis-Tris** bis(2-hydroxyethyl)amino-tris(hydroxymethyl)methan. 19, 30, 37
- BN** blue native. 19, 30
- BN-PAGE** blue native polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis. 3, 7, 26, 29, 30, 33, 36, 37, 40, 41, 45
- CHAPS** 3-[(3-cholamidopropyl)dimethylammonio]-1-propanesulfonate. 45
- Cyc2_{Ac}** Cyc2 of *Acidithiobacillus ferrooxidans*. 14, 15, 41, 42
- Cyc2_{Gal}** Cyc2 of *Gallionellaceae* sp. culture KS. 5–7, 12, 14–18, 23, 25, 26, 30, 33–36, 39–45
- Cyc2_{Lep}** Cyc2 of *Leptospirillum* sp.. 15
- Cyc2_{PV-1}** Cyc2 of *Mariprofundus ferrooxidans* PV-1. 7, 14, 15, 39
- CYMAL-4** 4-cyclohexyl-1-pentyl- β -D-maltoside. 45
- CYMAL-5** 5-cyclohexyl-1-pentyl- β -D-maltoside. 19, 36, 37
- CYMAL-6** 6-cyclohexyl-1-pentyl- β -D-maltoside. 45
- DDM** dodecyl- β -D-maltosid. 19, 36, 37
- DM** decyl-maltoside. 45
- DMNG** decyl maltose neopentyl glycol. 45
- DMSO** dimethyl sulfoxide. 25
- EDTA** ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid. 7, 8, 15–20, 30, 31, 37–39, 42–44
- EMBL** European Molecular Biology Laboratory. 25
- FeOB** iron oxidising bacteria. 3, 4, 7, 12–15, 33, 39
- Fos-choline 12** *n*-dodecyl-phosphocholine. 45
- GDN** glyco-diosgenin. 45
- GUZ** molecular biology laboratory at the geo- and environmental center Tübingen. 27, 28, 52–55
- HCl** hydrochloric acid. 20–22, 28, 30
- HEPES** 2-[4-(2-hydroxyethyl)piperazin-1-yl]ethanesulfonic acid. 20, 27, 29–31, 36, 40
- IMG** Integrated Microbial Genomes & Microbiomes. 25
- LB** lysogeny broth (Lennox). 22, 23, 25, 26
- LDAO** lauryldimethylamine N-oxide. 45
- LDS** lithium dodecyl sulfate. 20, 29, 31, 35, 40, 45

- LMNG** lauryl maltose neopentyl glycol. 19, 36, 37
- LPS** lipopolysaccharide. 16
- MBP** maltose-binding protein. 37, 38, 42
- MMH** cellular and molecular microbiology laboratory at the institute for medical microbiology and hygiene Tübingen. 27, 28, 52–55
- OD₆₀₀** optical density at 600 nm wavelength. 25, 26
- OG** octyl- β -glucoside. 19, 36, 37
- OM** outer membrane. 3, 6, 7, 14–18, 26, 27, 29–31, 33, 35–45
- OmpA** outer membrane protein A. 18, 24
- OmpF** outer membrane protein F. 18
- pASK-IBA2** pASK-IBA2 plasmid without the *cyc2_{Gal}* gene sequence. 23–25, 35, 36, 40
- pASK-IBA2-cyc2** pASK-IBA2 plasmid with the *cyc2_{Gal}* gene sequence. 23–25, 35–37, 40, 41
- PIPES** 1,4-piperazinediethanesulfonic acid. 21
- PL** phospholipids. 16
- PVDF** polyvinylidene difluoride. 31
- SB** solubilization buffer. 21, 29
- SDS** sodium dodecyl sulfate. 8, 20, 21, 28, 29, 35, 36, 38, 40, 45
- SDS-PAGE** sodium dodecyl sulfate polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis. 2, 18, 26–29, 31, 35, 37–40, 45
- SOB** super optimal broth. 22, 23, 25
- TBST** tris-buffered saline with Tween[®] 20. 21, 31, 32
- TCA** trichloroacetic acid. 21, 31, 45
- TEMED** tetramethylethylenediamine. 27, 28
- Tet** tetracycline. 23, 24
- TMBZ** 3,3',5,5'-tetramethylbenzidine. 20, 21
- Tricine** N-(2-hydroxy-1,1-bis(hydroxymethyl)ethyl)glycine. 19
- Tris** 2-amino-2-(hydroxymethyl)propane-1,3-diol. 20–22, 28, 30
- Tween[®] 20** polyoxyethylene (20) sorbitan monooleate. 21, 55
- UDM** undecyl-maltoside. 45
- VE** vacuum electric. 30
- YT** yeast tryptone. 23, 26

Materials and Methods

The main aim of this thesis was to determine the localisation of the cytochrome domain within the OM protein *Cyc2_{Gal}* by utilising a proteinase K assay. For this purpose enough *Cyc2_{Gal}* had to be produced to detect it with sodium dodecyl sulfate polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis (SDS-PAGE). Therefore, *Cyc2_{Gal}* was heterologously overexpressed in the *E. coli* strain MC4100. The correct expression and insertion into the OM were assessed before conducting the assay.

The wild type strain MC4100 was chosen because wild type strains have been shown to have a more stable membrane than those with the knocked out gene sequences coding for OM porins such as outer membrane protein A (OmpA) or outer membrane protein F (OmpF) [13]. An integer OM was desired to prevent proteinase K from penetrating the OM in the absence of EDTA. Another wild type *E. coli* strain (MT56) was tested as well. However, MT56_pEC86 grew slower than MC4100_pEC86 so the later one was chosen for further analysis.

2.1 Handling of Materials and Chemicals

All chemicals used were at least of analytical grade, see list of chemicals (Table A.2) for detailed information. The instruments are listed in detail in the list of instruments (Table A.1). Prior to use, all microcentrifugation tubes were sterilised by autoclavation. All glassware was washed in a dishwasher. The plates utilised to prepare agar plates were taken from bag under sterile conditions. Sterile conditions were established either through the proximity to a flame or by utilising a clean bench.

2.2 Solutions and Media

All solutions and media which were used for this study are listed in Table 2.1 and Table 2.2, respectively.

Table 2.1: List of Solutions with final concentration and description of preparation.

Solution	Final Concentration	Preparation
ACA/glycerol	250 mM ACA 50 % (w/v) glycerol	Mixing 0.681 g ACA with 3.963 ml glycerol and filling up to 10 ml with Milli-Q® water.

Table 2.1 List of Solutions continued from previous page

Solution	Final Concentration	Preparation
AHTC solution	2.16 mM AHTC in ethanol	Dissolving 20 mg AHTC in 10 ml pure ethanol according to manufacturer. Mixing 100 μ l of that solution with 900 μ l ethanol. Storing at -20 $^{\circ}$ C and keeping from light.
Ampicillin	143 mM Ampicillin	Dissolving 500 mg ampicillin in 10 ml Milli-Q [®] water according to manufacturer. Storing at -20 $^{\circ}$ C.
APS solution	10% APS	Dissolving 0.1 g APS in 1 ml Milli-Q [®] water. Storing at -20 $^{\circ}$ C. [11].
BN anode buffer	500 mM Bis-Tris	Dissolving 104.6 g Bis-Tris in 1 l Milli-Q [®] water.
BN cathode buffer	500 mM Tricine 150 mM Bis-Tris 0.2% (w/v) SERVA Blue G	Dissolving 44.79 g Tricine, 15.69 g Bis-Tris and 1 g SERVA Blue G in 500 ml Milli-Q [®] water by mixing over night.
BN loading buffer	5% (w/v) SERVA Blue G in ACA/glycerol	Mixing 25 mg SERVA Blue G and 450 μ l ACA/glycerol.
Chloramphenicol	105.22 mM Chloramphenicol in ethanol	Dissolving 340 mg chloramphenicol in 10 ml pure ethanol according to manufacturer. Storing at -20 $^{\circ}$ C.
Coomassie destaining solution	2% (w/v) ortho-phosphoric acid 85% 10% (w/v) ethanol	Mixing 11.75 ml 85% phosphoric acid with 50 ml pure ethanol.
Coomassie staining solution	5% (w/v) $\text{AlSO}_4 \cdot 16\text{H}_2\text{O}$ 0.02% (w/v) SERVA Blue G 2% (v/v) ortho-phosphoric acid 85% 10% (v/v) ethanol	Dissolving 100 g $\text{AlSO}_4 \cdot 16\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in 1 l pure ethanol and adding 0.4 g SERVA Blue G. Adding 47 ml phosphoric acid (85%) and filling up to 2 l with Milli-Q [®] water. [16].
Detergent solution	10% (w/w) detergent (LMNG, DDM, OG or CYMAL-5)	Weighing a spatulas tip detergent in a microcentrifugation tube. Adding Milli-Q [®] water. E.g. 63 μ l Milli-Q [®] water were added to 7 mg detergent. Mixing carefully by flicking with finger.
EDTA solution	0.5 M EDTA	Dissolving 18.61 g $\text{EDTA} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in 80 ml Milli-Q [®] water. Adjusting to pH 8.0 with NaOH. Sterile filtering and storing at 4 $^{\circ}$ C. [24].
Glucose solution	1 M glucose	Dissolving 9.008 g glucose in 50 ml Milli-Q [®] water.

Table 2.1 List of Solutions continued from previous page

Solution	Final Concentration	Preparation
Glycerol solution	80 % glycerol	Adding 80 ml glycerol in 20 ml Milli-Q [®] water.
Glycine stock solution	1 M glycine	Dissolving 3.754 g glycine in 50 ml Milli-Q [®] water.
Heme staining solution	1.251 mM TMBZ 0.175 M sodium acetate	Mixing 15 ml 4.17 mM TMBZ solution with 35 ml 0.25 M sodium acetate solution directly before use. [59].
Heme washing solution	0.175 M sodium acetate 30 % (v/v) isopropanol	Mixing 70 ml 0.25 M sodium acetate solution with 30 ml isopropanol. [59].
HEPES pH 7.4	10 mM HEPES	Dissolving 23.8 g HEPES in 90 ml Milli-Q [®] water, adjusting to pH 7.4 with NaOH and filling up with Milli-Q [®] water to 100 ml. Sterile filtering. Storing at 4 °C. Diluting 500 µl of that solution in 45.5 ml Milli-Q [®] water. Storing at 4 °C. [37]
Laemmlli solution	1 % (w/v) SDS 1.9 M glycine 248 mM Tris base	Dissolving 10 g SDS, 144.2 g glycine and 30 g Tris base in 1 l Milli-Q [®] water. [32].
LDS sample buffer 2×	100 mM Tris base 4 % (w/v) LDS 2 mM EDTA 20 % (v/v) glycerol 0.02 % (w/v) bromphenol blue	Mixing 5 ml 1 M Tris-HCl pH 7.4 buffer with 10 ml 20 % (w/v) LDS solution, 0.2 ml 0.5 M EDTA solution and 10 ml glycerol. Filling up with Milli-Q [®] water to 50 ml. Adding 10 mg bromphenol blue. [37].
LDS solution	20 % (w/v) LDS	Dissolving 20 g LDS in 100 ml Milli-Q [®] water. [37].
MgCl ₂ solution	2 M MgCl ₂	Dissolving 20.330 g MgCl ₂ · 6 H ₂ O in 50 ml Milli-Q [®] water.
MgSO ₄ solution	2 M MgSO ₄	Dissolving 24.648 g MgSO ₄ · 7 H ₂ O in 50 ml Milli-Q [®] water.
<i>N</i> -lauroyl sarcosine	2 % (w/v) <i>N</i> -lauroyl sarcosine	Dissolving 0.2 g <i>N</i> -lauroyl sarcosine in 10 ml 10 mM HEPES pH 7.4 solution. Storing at 4 °C. [37]
No-LDS sample buffer	100 mM Tris base 2 mM EDTA 20 % (v/v) glycerol 0.02 % (w/v) bromphenol blue	Mixing 5 ml 1 M Tris-HCl pH 7.4 buffer with 0.2 ml 0.5 M EDTA solution and 10 ml glycerol. Filling up with Milli-Q [®] water to 50 ml. Adding 10 mg bromphenol blue. [37].

Table 2.1 List of Solutions continued from previous page

Solution	Final Concentration	Preparation
Protease-Inhibitor Mix		Dissolving Protease-Inhibitor Mix HP PLUS by SERVA in 1 ml 90 % DMSO according to manufacturer.
Proteinase K solution	0.1 % (w/v) proteinase K	Dissolving 1 mg proteinase K in 1 ml Milli-Q [®] water.
SB-buffer	250 mM Tris base 20 % (v/v) glycerol 8 % (w/v) SDS 0.05 % (w/v) bromphenol blue	Mixing 5 ml 1 M Tris-HCl pH 6.8 with 5 ml 80 % glycerol, 1.6 g SDS and 0.01 g bromphenol blue. Filling up to 16 ml with Milli-Q [®] water. Dissolving by shaking at room temperature. Filling up to 20 ml with Milli-Q [®] water. Before use: Adding 100 μ l beta-mercaptoethanol to 400 μ l of the solution and diluting 4 \times with Milli-Q [®] water. Modified after Laemmli [32].
SDS solution	10 % (w/v) SDS	Dissolving 10 g SDS in 100 ml Milli-Q [®] water. [11]
Sodium acetate solution	0.25 M sodium acetate	Dissolving 8.35 g sodium acetate trihydrate in 250 ml Milli-Q [®] water. Adjusting to pH 5 with acetic acid.
TB buffer	10 mM PIPES 250 mM KCl 15 mM CaCl ₂ 55 mM MnCl ₂	Dissolving 1.512 g PIPES, 9.319 g KCl and 1.103 g CaCl ₂ · 2H ₂ O in 500 ml Milli-Q [®] water. Adjusting to pH 6.7 with KOH. Adding 5.047 g MnCl ₂ · 4 H ₂ O. Sterile filtering. Storing at 4 °C. [26].
TBST buffer	20 mM Tris base 150 mM NaCl 0.1 % (v/v) Tween [®] 20	Dissolving 24 g Tris base and 88 g NaCl in 900 ml Milli-Q [®] water. Adjusting to pH 7.6 with HCl. Filling up to 1 l with Milli-Q [®] water. Mixing 100 ml of this solution with 900 ml Milli-Q [®] water and 1 ml Tween [®] 20.
TCA solution	8.74 M TCA	Dissolving 14.28 g TCA in 10 ml Milli-Q [®] water. [53].
TMBZ solution	4.17 mM TMBZ in methanol	Adding 15 mg TMBZ to 15 ml methanol directly before solution is needed. Keeping from light.
Transfer buffer for western blot	24.8 mM Tris base 192 mM glycine 0.025 % (w/v) SDS 10 % (v/v) ethanol	Dissolving 30 g Tris base, 144 g glycine and 1.5 g SDS in 1 l Milli-Q [®] water. Mixing 100 ml of this solution with 100 ml ethanol and 800 ml Milli-Q [®] water.

Table 2.1 List of Solutions continued from previous page

Solution	Final Concentration	Preparation
Tris-HCl 1.5 M, pH 8.8	1.5 M Tris base	Dissolving 27.23 g Tris base in 80 ml Milli-Q [®] water. Adjusting to pH 8.8 with HCl. Filling up to 150 ml with Milli-Q [®] water. [11]
Tris-HCl 10 mM, pH 7.4	10 mM Tris base	Diluting 500 µl 1 M Tris-HCl buffer pH 7.4 in 45.5 ml Milli-Q [®] water.
Tris-HCl 1 M, pH 6.8	1 M Tris base	Dissolving 12.11 g Tris base in 80 ml Milli-Q [®] water. Adjusting to pH 6.8 with HCl. Filling up to 100 ml with Milli-Q [®] water. [11]
Tris-HCl 1 M, pH 7.4	1 M Tris base	Dissolving 12.11 g Tris base in 80 ml Milli-Q [®] water. Adjusting to pH 7.4 with HCl. Filling up to 100 ml with Milli-Q [®] water. [11].
Urea extraction solution	6 M urea 15 mM Tris base 100 mM glycine	Adding 0.75 ml 1 M Tris-HCl buffer and 5 ml 1 M glycine stock solution in 20 ml Milli-Q [®] water. Dissolving 18.01 g urea into this solution. Filling up to 50 ml with Milli-Q [®] water. Preparing directly before use. [37].

Table 2.2: List of Media with final concentration and description of preparation.

Medium	Final Concentrations	Preparation
Super optimal broth (SOB)	2% (w/v) tryptone 0.5% (w/v) yeast extract 8.6 mM NaCl 2.5 mM KCl 10 mM MgCl ₂ 10 mM MgSO ₄	Dissolving 20 g tryptone, 5 g yeast extract, 0.5 g NaCl and 0.187 g KCl in 1 l Milli-Q [®] water. Autoclaving. Adding sterile 5 ml 2 M MgCl ₂ solution and 5 ml 2 M MgSO ₄ solution. [21].
Lysogeny broth (LB)	1% (w/v) tryptone 0.5% (w/v) yeast extract 86 mM NaCl	Dissolving 20 g LB broth powder in 1 l Milli-Q [®] water according to manufacturer and autoclaving for sterilisation.

Table 2.2 List of Media continued from previous page

Medium	Final Concentrations	Preparation
Lysogeny broth agar plates	1.5 % (w/v) agar 1 % (w/v) tryptone 0.5 % (w/v) yeast extract 86 mM NaCl	Dissolving 8.75 g LB broth with agar in 250 ml Milli-Q [®] water according to manufacturer in a 500 ml Schott bottle while heating on a magnetic stirrer. Autoclaving. Subsequently, cooling to 50 °C while stirring. Adding 250 µl of the appropriate antibiotic sterily if desired. Pouring 20 ml medium into each plate sterily and letting the plates cool. Storing at 4 °C in a sterile bag.
SOC broth	20 mM glucose in SOB medium	Adding 20 ml sterile filtered 1 M glucose solution in 1 l SOB medium sterily. [21, 62]
2× yeast tryptone (YT)	1.6 % (w/v) tryptone 1 % (w/v) yeast extract 86 mM NaCl	Dissolving 31 g 2×YT medium powder in 1 l Milli-Q [®] water according to manufacturer. Transferring the medium to 50 ml Erlenmeyer flasks adding 25 ml medium to each flask. Autoclaving.

2.3 Plasmids

pEC86 Plasmid

The pEC86 plasmid was kindly provided by Karlsruhe Institute of Technology Institute for Applied Biology Department of Applied Biology. It carries the *ccm* gene cluster which is needed for the maturation of *c*-type cytochromes under aerobic conditions in *E. coli* [38]. *E. coli*'s endogenous proteins that are responsible for maturation of *c*-type cytochromes are only active under anaerobic conditions as *E. coli* usually does not produce these proteins under aerobic conditions [38]. Therefore, *cyc2_{Gal}* expression in *E. coli* requires pEC86.

The pEC86 plasmid provides resistance to chloramphenicol as it carries the gene for chloramphenicol transferase [38]. Thus, 1 µl chloramphenicol solution was added per 1 ml medium (final concentration: 0.105 mM) to media used to grow cultures of cells transformed with pEC86 plasmid.

PASK-IBA2 and PASK-IBA2-cyc2 Plasmids

The pASK-IBA2 plasmid was obtained from the Max Planck Institute for Developmental Biology Department 1. pASK-IBA2 was cloned with the *cyc2_{Gal}* gene sequence optimised for expression in *E. coli* to obtain the pASK-IBA2-cyc2 plasmid and kindly provided by Stefanie Becker. The pASK-IBA2-cyc2 plasmid carries the *cyc2_{Gal}* gene (Figure 3.1). Hence, it enables the *E. coli* cells to produce Cyc2_{Gal}. The expression is under control of a Tet promoter, thus induced by AHTC [57].

For the translocation of Cyc2_{Gal} through the cytoplasmic membrane, the protein requires a signal peptide [31]. Cyc2_{Gal}'s signal peptide was predicted with SignalP using the setting for gram-negative

bacteria [3]. The a.a. sequence used is shown in section 2.5. The predicted signal peptide was replaced by the signal peptide of OmpA. Thus, the pASK-IBA2-cyc2 plasmid carries an *ompA* signal gene sequence.

Both pASK-IBA2 and pASK-IBA2-cyc2 carry an ampicillin resistance gene. Thus, 1 μ l ampicillin solution was added per 1 ml medium (final concentration: 0.143 mM) to media used to grow cultures of cells transformed with pASK-IBA2 or pASK-IBA2-cyc2.

2.4 Strains

All wild type bacteria strains and genetically transformed strains, which were used in this study, are listed in Table 2.3.

Table 2.3: List of wild type bacteria strains and genetically transformed strains used for this study.

Strain	Description
MC4100	Wild type <i>E. coli</i> strain. Kindly provided by Prof. Samuel Wagner.
MC4100_pEC86	MC4100 strain transformed with the pEC86 plasmid.
MC4100_pEC86_pASK-IBA2	MC4100_pEC86 strain transformed with the pASK-IBA2 plasmid.
MC4100_pEC86_pASK-IBA2-cyc2	MC4100_pEC86 strain transformed with the pASK-IBA2-cyc2 plasmid.
MT56	Wild type <i>E. coli</i> strain. Kindly provided by Prof. Samuel Wagner.
MT56_pEC86	MT56 strain transformed with the pEC86 plasmid.
DH5 α TM	<i>E. coli</i> strain. Kindly provided by Prof. Lars Angenent.

2.5 Secondary Structure Prediction

A secondary structure prediction for *Cyc2_{Gal}* was performed with PSIPRED 4.0 [10, 28]. The a.a. sequence as published in He et al. [22] shown below was retrieved from Integrated Microbial Genomes & Microbiomes (IMG) and used for the secondary structure prediction.

>2566082742 hypothetical protein

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MKKIALSLAGVLAATAFAPEASAIPSFARQTGMACSACHFQHFPVLNSFG
MAFKSAGYTMGAQSKIEGEHLSIPDTLNASVLLKIRYQKTINGVDTAANA
AMSGATTNSGQWQMPDEMSMFLGGRAAENIGFVIEGNLAGNNAAGNGGIA
TGFKMPFMFDAGGAKVGVVFPFWDVLPAGHYELSSSGMVRGLRWSEDRS
SIAAANFVGLNNGAATGLAFVAKNDMGYINWTRWSPTQAGSLGGAGTKQF
KANWVRLAATPNYADWNMHIGLGFMSGSTNQVAATPVDRKGSTLDFQGG
TQLGGKDFSLYASYARAPGGAGTTNAYNNVAGVNNPNAKKAFQIGADYSV
IPHLHLGASYLDGDTGAAALNKDKAFMIQGIYDMVQNVALHASYTKYSG
SVYDLGGAKDKTVAGNSGDSLLMFMLEASF
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2.6 Expression of *Cyc2_{Gal}* in MC4100_pEC86_pASK-IBA2-cyc2

For the expression of *cyc2_{Gal}* a series of steps was needed. Heat-shock competent cells were prepared and transformed with the pEC86 plasmid. Preparation of heat-shock competent cells and transformation were repeated to insert the pASK-IBA2 plasmid with (pASK-IBA2-cyc2) and without (pASK-IBA2) the *cyc2_{Gal}* gene sequence. Subsequently, expression was conducted.

Preparation of Heat-Shock Competent Cells

Stocks of heat-shock competent cells were made based on Inoue et al. [26] with variations suggested by the European Molecular Biology Laboratory (EMBL) [15].

A single colony was picked from an LB agar plate under sterile conditions, transferred to 2 ml LB medium in a glass tube sterilely and incubated over night at 37 °C while shaking (200 rpm). 250 ml SOB medium in a 1 l flask were inoculated with the pre-culture under sterile conditions. The culture was incubated over night at room temperature while shaking (200 rpm) to an optical density (OD₆₀₀) value of 0.4 to 0.6. When right OD₆₀₀ value was reached, the flask was placed on ice for 10 min and then the cells were pelleted in five 50 ml Falcon tubes at 4000 rpm for 10 min at 4 °C. The supernatant was cast away and cells were resuspended in 20 ml ice cold TB solution per tube and stored on ice for 10 min before they were transferred to two 50 ml Falcon tubes and spun again at 4000 rpm for 10 min at 4 °C. The supernatant was decanted and cells were resuspended in 10 ml ice cold TB solution and 0.7 ml DMSO per tube and then placed on ice for 10 min. 100 µl and 500 µl aliquots were prepared in 1.5 ml microcentrifugation tubes and frozen in liquid N₂ immediately. The heat-shock competent cells were stored at -80 °C.

Transformation

Heat-shock transformation was used to insert plasmids into the cell. The protocol by Inoue et al. [26] was used with changes proposed by EMBL [62]. The required number of 1.5 ml microcentrifugation

tubes was pre-chilled on ice (one tube is required per plasmid variation) and the required amount of competent cells was thawed on ice. 50 μ l of competent cells were pipetted into each pre-chilled tube and 1 μ l plasmid was added. The tubes were incubated for 1 h on ice, heat shocked for 45 s at 42 °C and placed on ice again for 2 min. Then 800 μ l SOC medium were added to the tube and it was incubated for 1 h at 37 °C. Afterwards, 10 μ l or 100 μ l of the transformed cells were plated on LB agar containing the appropriate antibiotics under sterile conditions and incubated over night at 37 °C [62]. Whether 10 μ l or 100 μ l of cells were used depended on the ability of the culture to grow. In most cases 10 μ l were sufficient but usually two plates with different amounts of cells were incubated and a colony from the plate with more distinct colonies was used for further analysis.

Gene Expression

Expression was conducted after the protocol in Londer [38], Wollmann et al. [65] with small alterations. The expression was conducted in 2 \times yeast tryptone (YT) medium.

A pre-culture was prepared by sterilely picking a colony into a tube containing 2 ml LB medium and incubating at 37 °C over night while shaking (200 rpm). 250 μ l pre-culture were added to 25 ml 2 \times YT medium under sterile conditions and incubated at 30 °C and shaking (200 rpm) until an OD₆₀₀ of 0.5 to 0.8 was reached. Expression was then induced by sterilely adding 25 μ l of 2.16 mM AHTC solution according to manufacturer (final concentration: 2.16 μ M). Flasks were incubated over night at 30 °C and 200 rpm shaking.

2.7 Plasmid Amplification

The plasmids were amplified by using *E. coli* strain DH5 α TM. Therefore, the cells were transformed with the plasmid that had to be amplified and a colony was picked and added in a tube containing 2 ml LB medium and appropriate antibiotics. The culture was incubated over night at 37 °C and 200 rpm. Afterwards, the culture was transferred to a 2 ml microcentrifugation tube and centrifuged at 10 000 \times g for 1 min at room temperature.

To isolate the plasmid, the Plasmid Miniprep Kit I, peqGOLD (by VWR) was used and the instructions in the product manual [40] were complied with a few alterations which are as follows. Prior to lysis the cell pellet was frozen for 10 min at -20 °C and thawed, subsequently. This step was added to enhance cell lysis. Furthermore, the Elution Buffer was heated to 70 °C to remove any DNAses potentially contained in the buffer. After amplification, the plasmid concentration in the filtrate was measured using NanoDropTM.

2.8 Assessing *Cyc2_{Gal}* Production, Folding and Outer Membrane Insertion

To test whether the *cyc2_{Gal}* gene was being expressed by MC4100_pEC86_pASK-IBA2-cyc2, the OM was isolated and the sample was subjected to SDS-PAGE. The obtained gels were first stained using heme staining to only stain the heme complex in the *Cyc2_{Gal}* protein and afterwards, using Instant BlueTM or coomassie brilliant blue to stain all proteins. In order to check correct insertion into the outer membrane a variety of methods was used. The OM samples were subjected to urea extraction, (BN-PAGE) and heat shifting.

Outer Membrane Isolation

The isolation of the OM and the preparation of the solutions was conducted following the protocol by Leo et al. [37]. It was performed right after expression and the whole isolation procedure was performed on ice. All centrifugation steps were performed at 4 °C. The culture obtained during expression was centrifuged for 10 min at 4000 ×g in a 50 ml Falcon tube to pellet the cells, the supernatant was cask away. Afterwards, cells were resuspended in 2 ml cold 10 mM HEPES buffer pH 7.4 and centrifuged again for 10 min at 4000 ×g, the supernatant was discarded. At this point cells were stored at -80 °C if not needed immediately. For proteinase K assay, fresh cells were used without freezing, the assay was conducted after this washing step and isolation continued after the assay was finished. Now, cells were resuspended in 1.5 ml 10 mM HEPES buffer pH 7.4 and samples were moved to 2 ml microcentrifugation tubes. Cells were lysed by sonication (Sonicator Sonoplus HD 2200 (probe: UW 2200)) at ~30 % power and 5 cycle. Ultrasound was applied for ~10 s, samples were cooled down on ice and then sonicated again. This was repeated approximately 5 times until samples became less opaque than they were at the beginning. During sonication formation of foam was to be avoided as this could have led to protein denaturation [14]. Between samples the sonicator tip was washed with 70 % ethanol and demineralised water to prevent sample contamination. The lysate was centrifuged for 2 min at 15 600 ×g to pellet any unlysed cells. The supernatant was moved to a new 2 ml microcentrifugation tube and centrifuged at 15 600 ×g for 30 min to pellet the membrane. The supernatant, containing the soluble proteins, was discarded, except when used for western blotting in the proteinase K assay. The membrane pellet with its distinct brownish colour was resuspended in 200 µl 10 mM HEPES buffer pH 7.4. 200 µl *N*-lauroyl sarcosine solution (2 % (w/v)) were added to the suspension and the sample was incubated for 30 min at room temperature while shaking (300 rpm) to solubilize the inner membrane. The sample was then centrifuged again at 15 600 ×g for 30 min to pellet outer membrane and supernatant was decanted afterwards. The pellet was washed with 200 µl 10 mM HEPES buffer pH 7.4 but not resuspended and centrifuged for 10 min at 15 600 ×g. The supernatant was decanted and OM pellet could be stored on ice at 4 °C over night if needed.

SDS-PAGE and Staining

SDS-PAGE

For SDS-PAGE that was performed in the molecular biology laboratory at the Geo- and Environmental Center Tuebingen (GUZ), gels were hand cast. For hand-casting the gels Mini-PROTEAN® Tetra handcast system was used. A 0.75 mm spacer plate and a short plate were put in a clamp together and fixed at a stand. 70 % ethanol was poured between the glass plates to check for leaks, if tight, ethanol was discarded. The gels were mixed according to Table 2.4 in 50 ml Falcon tubes under the fume hood. Then 8 µl TEMED were added to the running gel, the gel components were mixed quickly and then poured between the glass plates using a graduated pipette until approximately 2 cm under the upper edge of the glass plate. The gel was covered with isopropanol to achieve an even surface and left to polymerise for at least 30 min. Afterwards, the isopropanol was discarded. 6 µl TEMED were added to the stacking gel which was then mixed and poured on top of the running gel using a graduated pipette. A comb with ten wells was inserted into the gel and the gel was left to polymerise for another 15 min. Afterwards, the glass plates with the gel inside were removed from the handcast system and stored in a plastic bag with water at 4 °C for up to one week. These gels were used for heat modifiability assay and the OM sample in the proteinase K assay. At the cellular and molecular microbiology laboratory at the institute for medical microbiology and hygiene Tuebingen (MMH) ready gels (SERVAGel™ TG PRiME™ 8 - 16 %) were used. This was the case for the SDS-PAGE after urea extraction and the western blot gel from proteinase K assay.

Table 2.4: Ingredients for SDS gels (from Laemmli [32] with alterations).

Gel	Ingredient	Volume
12 % SDS-PAGE-gel (running gel)	Milli-Q [®] water	6.6 ml
	30 % Rotiforese [®] (acrylamid mix)	8.0 ml
	1.5 M Tris-HCl, pH 8.8	5.0 ml
	10 % SDS	200 µl
	10 % APS	200 µl
	TEMED	8 µl (added later)
5 % SDS-PAGE-gel (stacking gel)	Milli-Q [®] water	4.2 ml
	30 % Rotiforese [®] (acrylamid mix)	1.0 ml
	1 M Tris-HCl, pH 6.8	760 µl
	10 % SDS	60 µl
	10 % APS	60 µl
	TEMED	6 µl (added later)

The gels were placed into the SDS-PAGE running chamber and the system was filled with Laemmli solution. In the now assembled chamber, 5 µl marker and 20 µl samples were loaded onto the gels. The markers used were PageRuler™ Plus Prestained Protein Ladder (by thermofisher scientific) at the GUZ and Precision Plus Protein™ All Blue Prestained Protein Standards (by bio-rad) at the MMH.

The SDS-PAGE was run at 100 V, 400 mA and 3 W until the marker reached the end of the stacking gel, then the voltage was increased to 200 V until the marker had reached the end of the gel. After running the SDS-PAGE the gel was removed from glass plates carefully and once washed with deionized water.

Heme Staining

The heme staining was carried out as published by Thomas et al. [59]. The protocol was kindly provided by Prof. Carlos Salgueiro (Universidade NOVA de Lisboa). After SDS-PAGE, the gel was transferred to heme staining solution and incubated for at least 30 min and up to 1 h in the dark, with shaking every 15 min. 300 µl 30 % H₂O₂ were added and gel was incubated in the dark for another 30 min with constant shaking. Finally, the gel was twice washed with heme washing solution to reduce the background and enhance staining intensity.

Staining with Instant Blue™

The Instant Blue™ staining solution was used according to the manufacturer. The gel was placed in Instant Blue™ and constantly shaken for at least 15 min until protein bands were clearly visible. However, incubating gel in Instant Blue[®] does not pose the risk of overstaining.

Staining with Coomassie Brilliant Blue

Coomassie staining was used at the MMH to achieve the same result as was usually achieved by Instant Blue™ staining. Thus this method was used to stain the gel obtained after urea extraction

and the destaining part of this method was used to destain the BN-PAGE gel, as urea extraction and BN-PAGE were conducted in this laboratory.

To stain the gel, it was placed in coomassie staining solution over night while shaking. When completely stained, the gel was placed in destaining solution until blue protein bands were visible on a clear background.

Heat Modifiability Assay

The heat modifiability method was used to observe the difference in apparent molecular weight between denaturated and native proteins [37]. Unheated proteins are meant to be resistant to SDS denaturation [37] which means that they should stay folded during SDS-PAGE and run at a different apparent molecular weight. The assay was applied to samples in prior to SDS-PAGE. In addition to the folding of the protein the heat modifiability can also be useful to gather information on whether the protein is a monomer or multimer as monomeric proteins should migrate through the gel faster and multimeric proteins slower when in native stage [37].

For the heat modifiability assay conducted in this thesis LDS was used instead of SDS. LDS has similar properties as SDS but is recommended for combination with heme staining.

The sample from 2×25 ml expression was resuspended in 40 µl 10 mM HEPES buffer pH 7.4 after OM isolation. 10 µl each were moved to four new 1.5 ml microcentrifugation tubes. To three of the tubes 10 µl 2×LDS sample buffer were added and to the last tube 10 µl no-LDS sample buffer was added. The tube without LDS was kept on ice as well as one of the tubes containing 2×LDS. The other two tubes were incubated at 94 °C for 10 min and 20 min, respectively. The condensed water in the heated tubes was spun down using a small table centrifuge. This protocol was adapted from Leo et al. [37]. Samples were then subjected to SDS-PAGE. The SDS-PAGE chamber was kept on ice to ensure protein denaturation did not occur due to temperature rise.

Urea Extraction

The urea extraction method was used to assess whether proteins could be solubilised by urea from the OM. Correctly inserted and folded proteins should remain in the membrane whereas only weakly associated proteins would be extracted [37].

For urea extraction a protocol by Leo et al. [37] was used with small alterations. An OM pellet from a 50 ml expression culture was resuspended in 200 µl 10 mM HEPES buffer pH 7.4 and 50 µl aliquots were moved to ultracentrifugation tubes. 950 µl 10 mM HEPES buffer pH 7.4 were added to one tube and 950 µl 6 M urea extraction solution to each of the other tubes. The samples were incubated for 1 h at room temperature and then ultracentrifuged at 25 °C and 153 700 ×g for 90 min. The supernatant was discarded and the samples were resuspended in 20 µl SB-buffer. Afterwards, samples were heated to 94 °C for 10 min and the condensed water in the tube was spun down. Finally, samples were subjected to SDS-PAGE.

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Appendices

A.1 List of Instruments

Table A.1: List of instruments. The list shows the instrument, the supplier and the laboratory where the instrument was used.

Instrument	Supplier	Lab.
Table-Microcentrifuge 5418 R (rotor: FA-45-18-11)	Eppendorf	GUZ
Centrifuge 5430 R (rotor: F-35-6-30)	Eppendorf	GUZ
Optima Ultracentrifuge (rotor: TLA-55)	Beckmann Coulter	MMH
Sorvall™ LYNX™ 6000 Centrifuge (rotor: Fiberlite™ F14-14 x 50cy)	Thermo Scientific	GUZ
Table-Microcentrifuge 5424 R (rotor: FA-45-24-11)	Eppendorf	MMH
Mini Centrifuge Rapid	LTF Labortechnik	GUZ
Mini-PROTEAN® SDS chamber	bio-rad	GUZ
BlueVertical™ PRiME™ SDS chamber	SERVA	MMH
BlueBlot Semi-Dry Blotter	SERVA	MMH
Gel documentation Fusion SL	Vilber Lourmat	GUZ
Odyssey™ infrared imaging system	li-cor	MMH
Incubator Hood TH 30 (Rack system Combifix SM)	Edmund Bühler	GUZ
Shaker DRS-12	neoLab	GUZ
ThermoMixer®	Eppendorf	GUZ MMH
Incubator	Binder	GUZ
Autoclave VE-40	Systec	GUZ
Autoclave 5075 ELV	tuttnauer Systec	GUZ
Autoclave HX-430	Systec	GUZ
Clean bench Nuair 126-300E	ibs technomara	GUZ
NanoDrop ND-1000 Spectrophotometer	Thermo Scientific	GUZ
Multiskan GO	Thermo Scientific	GUZ

Table A.1 List of instruments continued from previous page

Instrument	Supplier	Lab.
Sonicator Sonoplus HD 2200 (probe: UW 2200)	Bandelin	GUZ
Vortex-Genie®	Scientific Industries	GUZ MMH
Magnetic stirrer RCT standard safety control	LLG Labware	GUZ
inoLab® pH 7110	WTW	GUZ
Water purification system GenPure™ Pro UV	Thermo Scientific	GUZ
VIP insulation 830L Green Line	Skadi	GUZ
Freezer DF8520GL	Skadi	GUZ
Self Contained Ice Machine AF 80	Scotsman	GUZ
Self Contained Ice Machine AF 103	Scotsman	GUZ

A.2 List of Chemicals

Table A.2: List of Chemicals with chemical name, name of supplier and the laboratory where the chemical was used.

Chemical	Supplier	Lab.
2×YT medium powder microbial growth medium	Sigma Aldrich	GUZ
5-Cyclohexyl-1-Pentyl- β -D-Maltoside (CYMAL-5)	Anatrace	MMH
6-Aminocaproic acid (ACA) $\geq 99\%$	Sigma Aldrich	MMH
Acetic acid	Honeywell Fluka	GUZ
Acetone		GUZ
Aluminium sulfate hexadecahydrate	Sigma Aldrich	MMH
Ammoniumperoxodisulfat $\geq 98\%$, p.a., ACS	Roth	GUZ
Ampicillin Sodium salt $\geq 99\%$, for molecular biology and biochemistry	Roth	GUZ
Anhydrotetracycline hydrochloride	iba-lifesciences	GUZ
Anti-MBP Monoclonal Antibody	NEB	GUZ
Bis(2-hydroxyethyl)amino-tris(hydroxymethyl)methan (Bis-Tris)	Applchem	MMH
Bromophenol Blue	Applchem	MMH
Bromophenol Blue, sodium salt, pure, water soluble, indicator	Acros organics	GUZ
Calcium chloride dihydrate Puriss. p.a. ACS Reagent, Reag. Ph. Eur., $\geq 99\%$	Honeywell Fluka	GUZ
Chloramphenicol $\geq 98.5\%$, Ph.Eur., für die Biochemie	Roth	GUZ
D-Glucose anhydrous Analytical reagent grade	Thermo Fisher Scientific	GUZ

Table A.2 List of chemicals continued from previous page

Chemical	Supplier	Lab.
Dimethylsulfoxid $\geq 99.5\%$, BioScience-Grade, für die Molekularbiologie Dimethyl sulphoxide	Roth	GUZ
Dodecyl Maltoside (DDM)	Anatrace	MMH
Ethanol	Merck	GUZ
Ethylendiamin-tetraessigsäure $\geq 99\%$, p.a., ACS Ethylendiamine tetraacetic acid	Roth	GUZ
Glycerol	Applichem	MMH
Glycerol puriss., meets analytical specification of Ph. Eur., BP, USP, FCC, E422, anhydrous, 99-101 % (alkalimetric)	Sigma Aldrich	GUZ
Glycine	Roth	MMH
Glycine for electrophoresis, $\geq 99\%$	Sigma Aldrich	GUZ
Goat Anti-Mouse IgG DyLight 800	Thermo Pierce	GUZ
HEPES $\geq 99.5\%$ (titration)	Sigma Aldrich	GUZ
Hydrochloric acid	Merck	GUZ
Hydrogen peroxide solution 30 % (w/w) in H ₂ O, contains stabilizer	Sigma Aldrich	GUZ
Instant Blue A Coomassie Based Staining Solution for Protein Gels	expedeon	GUZ
Isopropanol Molecular Biology Grade	Thermo Fisher Scientific	GUZ
Kaliumchlorid $\geq 99.5\%$, p.a., ACS, ISO Potassium chloride	Roth	GUZ
Lauryl Maltose Neopentyl Glycol (LMNG)	Anatrace	MMH
LB Broth (Lennox) Highly-referenced microbial growth powder medium, low salt, suitable for salt-sensitive E.coli culture	Sigma Aldrich	GUZ
LB Broth with Agar (Lennox) Highly-referenced microbial growth powder medium with Agar, low salt, suitable for salt-sensitive E. coli culture	Sigma Aldrich	GUZ
Lithium dodecyl sulfate BioReagent, for molecular biology, suitable for electrophoresis	Sigma Aldrich	GUZ
Magnesium chloride hexahydrate for analysis EMSURE ACS, Reag. Ph Eur	Merck	GUZ
Magnesium sulfate heptahydrate for analysis EMSURE ACS, Reag. Ph Eur	Merck	GUZ
Manganese(II) chloride tetrahydrate for analysis EMSURE® ACS	Merck	GUZ
Methanol	Merck	GUZ
N-lauroylsarcosine sodium salt $\geq 97\%$ (HPLC)	Sigma Aldrich	GUZ
N-Tris-(hydroxymethyl)-methyl-glycin (Tricine)	Roth	MMH
NativeMark Unstained Protein Standard	Thermo Fisher Scientific	GUZ
NativeMark Unstained Protein Standard	Thermo Fisher Scientific	GUZ

Table A.2 List of chemicals continued from previous page

Chemical	Supplier	Lab.
Natriumchlorid $\geq 99.5\%$, p.a., ACS, ISO Sodium chloride	Roth	GUZ
Octyl Glucoside (OG)	Anatrace	MMH
Ortho-phosphoric acid 85 %	Merck	MMH
PageRuler Plus Prestained Protein Ladder	Thermo Fisher Scientific	GUZ
PIPES $\geq 99\%$ (titration)	Sigma Aldrich	GUZ
Potassium hydroxide Puriss. P.a. Reag. Ph. Eur., pellets, $\geq 85\%$	Honeywell Fluka	GUZ
Precision Plus Protein All Blue Prestained Protein Standards	bio-rad	GUZ
Protease-Inhibitor Mix HP PLUS	SERVA	GUZ
Proteinase K (from tritirachium album) chromatographically purified lyophilized 30 mAnsonU/mg for biochemistry and molecular biology	Merck	GUZ
Rotiforese Gel 30 (37.5:1) Gebrauchsfertige, gasstabilisierte, wässrige, 30% Acrylamidstammllösung mit 0.8% Bisacrylamid im Verhältnis 37.5:1	Roth	GUZ
SERVA Blue G	SERVA	GUZ
Sodium acetate anhydrous, ReagentPlus, $\geq 99\%$	Sigma Aldrich	GUZ
Sodium chloride	VWR	MMH
Sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS)	Roth	MMH
Sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS) BioUltra, for molecular biology, $\geq 99\%$ (GC)	Sigma Aldrich	GUZ
Sodium hydroxide puriss. p.a., ACS reagent, reg. Ph. Eur., $K \leq 0.02\%$, $\geq 98\%$, pellets	Merck	GUZ
TEMED $\geq 99\%$, p.a., für die Elektrophorese	Roth	GUZ
Tetramethylbenzidine $\geq 99\%$	Sigma Aldrich	GUZ
Trichloroacetic acid Analytical reagent grade	Thermo Fisher Scientific	GUZ
TRIS PUFFERAN $\geq 99.3\%$, Buffer Grade	Roth	GUZ
Tryptone enzymatic digest from Casein	Fluka Analytical	GUZ
Tween [®] 20	Sigma Aldrich	MMH
Urea powder, BioReagent, for molecular biology, suitable for cell culture	Sigma Aldrich	GUZ
Yeast Extract for microbiology	Sigma Aldrich	GUZ
β -Mercaptoethanol	Applichem	MMH